

22NRM01 TraMeXI

D5 - Report on the performance of at least 5 commercially available X-ray multimeters in laboratory and clinical conditions tested in at least 3 NMIs/DIs and 3 clinics enabling estimation of uncertainties related to measurements of different quantities. This report will include recommendations for an update of IEC 61676 and inclusion of other relevant QA parameters in new or existing standards and evidence submitted to TC 62 SC62C WG3 and IAEA CRP officers.

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Glossary

In this document the following acronym are used

CPRQ	Clinically relevant and Physical representative Radiation Qualities
HVL	1st Half-value Layer (HVL) in mm of aluminium (Al).
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IT	irradiation time in seconds (s).
K_{air}	Air kerma (mGy), in this deliverable it used as general term covering also air kerma rate (mGy/s).
kV	kilovoltage
PMMA	Polymethyl Methacrylate
PPV	practical-peak voltage
QA	quality assurance
SC	subcommittee
TC	technical committee
TF	total filtration in mm of aluminium (Al).
TV	tube voltage related quantities, which can be practical peak voltage, maximum tube voltage, and average tube voltage.
WG	working group
XMM	X-ray multimeter.

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1 Introduction

This report summarizes the performance of X-ray multimeters (XMMs) in laboratory and clinical conditions based on activities A3.1.4, A3.3.2., A3.4.1, A3.4.2, and A3.4.3 explained below and include recommendations for an update of IEC 61676 and inclusion of other relevant QA parameters in new or existing standards. This deliverable and related evidence is submitted to IEC SC62C WG3 and IAEA officers (Figure 1).

TraMeXI D5: XMM quantities: performance and inclusion into IEC standards

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D5-TraMeXI-Recommendations for an update of IEC 61676 and inclusion of XMM quantities.pdf
422 KB

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Dear Zakithi, Olivera and Wes,

I am happy to share with you TraMeXI deliverable number 5, a report on the performance of XMMs and recommendations for the inclusion of XMM quantities in new or existing standards. The results and recommendations were already discussed in the M36 and IEC meetings. This deliverable needs to be formally shared with you before it can be submitted to EURAMET for approval. I will also send you the final version once it has been approved by EURAMET.

Best regards,
Paula

Figure 1. Results were presented in the M36 meeting to the chief stakeholder and deliverable was sent to the IEC WG3 and IAEA officers.

2 Input activities

A 3.1.4 – Summary of XMM Requirements

Based on the analysis carried out in this activity, target uncertainties were defined for XMM clinical measurements and calibrations in terms of air kerma (K_{air}), tube voltage related quantities (TV) and half-value layer (HVL), as well as limits for variations due to influencing quantities.

A 3.3.2 – Primary PPV

This activity evaluated the feasibility of establishing a primary realization of the practical peak voltage (PPV) quantity using an aluminium filter, a PMMA phantom, and an imaging system, based on the definition of the quantity.

A 3.4.1 – XMM Calibration

In this activity, the calibration procedures developed in activities A3.2.2 – A3.2.5 were used to calibrate at least five different models of XMMs (with at least two different models in each calibration laboratory, ensuring at least two independent sets of results for each type), considering both standard radiation qualities and the new Clinically relevant and Physical representative Radiation Qualities (CPRQs). The number of XMMs calibrated during this activity exceeded the initial commitment.

A 3.4.2 – Clinical XMM Calibration

In this activity, the calibration procedures developed in activity A3.3.3 were used to calibrate at least five different models of XMMs in clinical settings, covering at least two conventional radiography units, two fluoroscopy or interventional units (with copper filtration), and two mammography units, considering the new radiation qualities (CPRQs) proposed in activity A1.1.4. The number of XMMs calibrated during this activity exceeded the initial commitment.

A 3.4.3 – Adjusted Beams

This activity assessed the robustness of XMM indications in terms of air kerma, HVL, and PPV by performing calibrations in standard radiation qualities and in the same radiation qualities adjusted by changing filtration or X-ray tube voltage.

3 Target uncertainties

The target uncertainties were determined based on a comprehensive evaluation combining four main sources: (i) a review of relevant literature, including applicable standards; (ii) an assessment of the current state of the art of clinical XMMs use, derived from a survey of medical physicists; (iii) an evaluation of state of the art calibration capabilities based on calibration and measurement capabilities (CMCs) published in the BIPM Key Comparison Database (KCDB); and (iv) an online questionnaire targeting calibration and testing laboratories across Europe. Each quantity was evaluated separately, and the resulting target uncertainties ($k = 2$) reflect a balance between current calibration capabilities, variability across laboratories, and requirements reported in standards and literature are presented in Table 1 [1].

Table 1. Requirements, current uncertainties and derived target measurement uncertainties ($k = 2$) for air kerma (K_{air}), tube voltage related quantities (TV), irradiation time (IT) and half-value layer (HVL) [1].

	K_{air}	TV	IT	HVL
Accuracy of X-ray system, maximum error				
Requirements for X-ray systems	5 % [2-4]	8 % (general) [5] 5 % (mammography) [6]	\pm (10 % +1 ms) [5]	>Specified value 5 % (mammography) [5]
Current uncertainties in calibrations ($k = 2$)				
Uncertainty from calibration labs (range)	<1 % - 4 %	<1 % - 10 %	<1 % - 10 %	1 % - 10 %
Uncertainty from calibration labs (50% point)	2 %	2 %	2 %	4 %
Target measurement uncertainties ($k = 2$)				
Target uncertainty (accuracy)	5 %	2 %	2 %	<<5 % for mammography
Target uncertainty (reproducibility)	1.5 %	1 %	1 %	Not specified

4 Primary PPV

By definition, PPV is specified as the voltage of a constant potential generator that results in the same kerma contrast as fluctuating voltage resulting from exposures using a real X-ray generator for a tube of 12° anode angulation and an inherent filtration of 2.5 mm Al equivalent. PPV has been introduced 1998 by Kramer et. al. [7] based on simulation data and it has later been taken up as IEC standard. While PPV is the only voltage quantity being defined by an IEC standard, its practical realization under clinical conditions has not been tested so far. This was conducted on A3.3.2 following the definition given in [7]. The contrast equivalent was determined following the PPV definition from the ratio of air kerma and pixel data measurements using a 10 cm thick PMMA phantom with and without a slab of 1 mm aluminium. The measurements were performed on several X-ray units using different types of XMM and ionization chambers from different manufacturers, and the X-ray device related image detectors. Data were taken under different exposure settings, such as with or without a grid, varying field sizes, varying amounts of additional filtration and several tube voltages. The percentage difference between the PPV as calculated from the contrast measurements and the kV set on the device was calculated. The result was further compared to peak tube voltage- and PPV-indications of the XMM.

The results showed a prominent influence of field size on the determination of the primary PPV. An increase in field size led to a higher percentage difference between the primary PPV and the nominal tube voltage set on the device. This behaviour was studied using XMM and image detectors. It was observed for both detectors but was larger for the XMM. Here, the range of the percentage difference for the largest field size ($40 \times 40 \text{ cm}^2$) was 20 % – 45 %, decreasing to less than 5 % for the smallest field size ($6 \times 6 \text{ cm}^2$). The

image detector showed a percentage difference in the range of 54 % – 75 % for the largest field size and 38 % – 52 % for the smallest. The effect results from scattered radiation incident on the detector and thus, reducing the contrast. The remaining difference for the pixel data results most likely from the fact that these detectors are never available as such but are covered and thus get exposed to harder filtered radiation. This effect could probably be overcome with the use of unshielded pixelized detectors. This, however, has not been tested in the frame of TraMeXI. Ionization chambers were also used for small field sizes, and the percentage difference obtained for the primary PPV and the nominal tube voltage set on the device was in the same range as those obtained for XMMs. Based on these results, the best approach for measuring the primary PPV would be to use an XMM or IC-chamber with a small field size.

PPV is specified for X-ray systems with 2.5 mm Al total filtration. XMMs indicate PPV also for harder filtered spectra. However, the accuracy of these values can be affected by the total filtration depending on the energy dependence of their response. The direct XMM readout is based on time-resolved voltage measurements. A direct determination of PPV from contrast values was evaluated for harder filtered spectra. The resulting primary PPV was observed to be significantly influenced by the additional filtration, and it deviated considerably from true values. Therefore, this primary PPV method is not recommended for use with harder filtered radiation.

5 XMM calibrations

Multiple X-ray multimeters were calibrated at several standards dosimetry laboratories (SDLs) using mammography, RQR and RQT radiation qualities, as well as non-standard clinically relevant and physical representative radiation qualities (CPRQ). The CPRQ spectra were proposed by the TraMeXI consortium, and they are based on the research presented in WP1 deliverables D1 and D2 and described in scientific publications [8, 9]. For general radiology, these spectra are based on RQR radiation qualities with additional copper filtration, with copper thicknesses ranging from 0.1 to 0.9 mm. For mammography a large range of different clinically relevant radiation qualities were covered. The calibrations covered key XMM measurement quantities, including air kerma (Ka), tube voltage related quantities (TV), half-value layer (HVL), irradiation time (IT), and total filtration (TF).

To ensure consistency across the traceability chain, the XMMs were also calibrated in clinical beams for air kerma, HVL, and TV over a range of radiation qualities. In cases where no reference values were available, a calibrated XMM was used to verify the exposure settings available in clinics.

Numerous calibrations of XMMs were conducted in laboratories and hospitals during the project. However, not all of these activities were documented here or reported in publications. Nevertheless, they contributed valuable data and insights that support this deliverable. The results presented in this document are therefore based primarily on published or submitted papers. These laboratory and clinical beam calibrations have led to four published scientific papers [8, 12 - 14] and an additional five papers that have been prepared and submitted [10 – 11, 15 - 17]. Together, these studies cover clinically relevant radiation qualities across multiple X-ray imaging modalities. Several XMM performance characteristics and influence quantities including air kerma rate, angle of incidence and detector rotation, stabilisation time, accuracy, resolution, and repeatability,

were investigated in the studies by Krzanovic et al. [7, 10]. However, the primary focus of the TraMeXI project and of this deliverable is the influence of radiation quality and energy dependence on XMM response, as these represent some of the largest contributors to measurement uncertainty in clinical X-ray dosimetry. The main findings and conclusions are summarized below.

5.1 Summary of scientific papers prepared

The core part of this activity was an extensive collaborative study in which the performance of 24 commercially available XMMs was evaluated in 11 NMI/DIs, covering 9 different XMM models from 6 manufacturers. The main results related to air kerma (rate) have already been reported in Krzanovic et al. [8] and summarised in Deliverable 3 (<https://zenodo.org/records/20088600>), and recommendations concerning updates of IEC 61674 for air kerma measurements were presented in Deliverable 4 (<https://zenodo.org/records/17184130>) covering both general radiology and mammography beams.

In this deliverable the focus is on the other quantities measured by XMMs. These results cover 25 commercially available XMMs that were evaluated in 10 NMI/DIs, covering 9 different XMM models from 6 manufacturers. The corresponding results are presented in another scientific paper by Krzanovic et al. that was prepared and submitted [10]. The main results are summarized in this deliverable, and all this data was used to define the recommended limits of variation in the chapters below.

In addition, Toroi et al. [11] calibrated eight XMMs from four manufacturers for air kerma, TV, and HVL using one laboratory and three clinical X-ray systems (2 general radiography and interventional systems). Reference values were established using traceable ionization chambers, high-voltage dividers, and spectrometric methods. Calibration coefficients were determined for both standard aluminium-filtered radiation qualities and an extended range including 0–0.9 mm of copper filtration. The study evaluated the energy dependence of the XMM response, the influence of X-ray system characteristics, and the effect of applying calibration coefficients on the accuracy and consistency of the measured quantities.

In the field of mammography, several publications were prepared [12 - 17] investigating the impact of calibration conditions and radiation quality selections on the performance of XMMs. Kojic et al. [12] studied four XMMs and Salomon et al [14] eight XMMs when evaluating the influence of anode/filter software settings used in calibrations. Both studies concluded that the energy dependence of XMM response is significant and that the correct selection of software settings is essential. Costa de Castro et al, [13] investigated six XMMs and Salomon et al [16] eight XMMs in studies assessing the impact of the compression paddle on XMM performance. Both studies showed that the compression paddle affects XMM response, particularly in TV and HVL measurements. Consequently, this additional variation in radiation quality, where nominally identical beam qualities are modified by the added filtration from the compression paddle, should be considered when defining IEC standard requirements for energy dependence of response. Kojic et al. [17] further investigated the influence of field size on HVL measurements and calibrations using five XMMs and concluded that XMMs are relatively insensitive to field size effects, at least when the compression paddle is positioned far from the detector. In addition, Salomon et al. [15] calibrated five commercially available XMMs for air kerma and HVL

both under primary-standard laboratory conditions and on ten clinical mammography systems from six manufacturers. An extensive range of radiation qualities was covered and the calibration coefficients obtained under laboratory and clinical conditions were also subsequently compared.

5.2 Summary of recommendations for general radiography beams

Three papers cover results for general radiology (>40 kV) [3, 5, 6]. For these radiation qualities, several XMM models were investigated and calibrated for all measured quantities, as described above. As concluded by Krzanovic et al. [8] and summarised in Deliverable 3 (<https://zenodo.org/records/20088600>), the relative energy dependence related variations of response for air kerma and air kerma rate stayed within $\pm 5\%$, meeting the requirements of the IEC 61674 standard [18] not only for IEC 61267 standard [19] RQR beams but throughout the specified operating range covering also copper filtered beams. However, certain XMM models showed a noticeable over-response at the lowest energy general radiography beam quality (RQR 2), which lies outside the minimum rated range currently specified in the IEC 61674 in the energy dependence of the response test. Toroi et al. [11] further extended the investigation to cover the full range of added copper filtrations and included both clinical radiography and interventional X-ray systems. Their results support the proposed $\pm 5\%$ acceptance limit and demonstrated the importance of including clinically relevant beam qualities in XMM performance evaluations.

For the XMM quantities other than air kerma (rate), the evaluation of the relative response changes associated with variations in photon spectra was performed using an approach analogous to that defined in IEC 61267 standard for air kerma, as described by Krzanovic et al. [10]. Variations of up to $\pm 5\%$ were observed for all voltage-related quantities (TV). Similar findings were reported by Toroi et al. [11]. However, Toroi et al. also identified significant difference in XMM performance between industrial calibration systems and clinical X-ray systems, even when matched radiation qualities were used. Under the limited testing conditions currently specified in the IEC 61676 [20], the energy dependence of response typically remained below 2.5 % in industrial beams and below 1.5 % in clinical beams. When the investigation was extended to include additional copper filtration, the observed variations increased to approximately 4 % and 2.9 %, respectively. These findings demonstrate that the specified range of influence quantities has a substantial effect on the observed performance and should therefore be carefully considered when defining updated acceptance limits and test conditions in future revision of IEC 61676.

For half-value layer (HVL) measurements under standard radiation conditions, the study by Krzanovic et al. [10] showed that most XMM responses demonstrated an energy dependence within $\pm 5\%$. However, for non-standard copper-filtered radiation qualities, the observed variation increased to as much as 10 %. Similar conclusions were reported by Toroi et al. [11], who found that most XMMs would comply with a $\pm 5\%$ energy-dependence limit under the reference conditions, whereas inclusion of the full range of clinically relevant radiation qualities increased the variations to approximately 7.5 %. In addition, some XMMs appeared to be more sensitive to the type of X-ray system used, with slightly larger variations observed for industrial calibration systems compared with clinical X-ray systems. These findings indicate that both radiation quality range and

X-ray system characteristics should be considered when defining performance requirements and acceptance limits for HVL measurements in future revisions of IEC standards.

The study by Krzanovic et al. [10] also covered total filtration (TF) and irradiation time measurements. For TF, the observed energy-dependence-related variations reached up to 20%, indicating a strong sensitivity of this quantity to changes in photon spectra and beam filtration. In contrast, irradiation time measurements were found to be relatively insensitive to radiation quality, with deviations remaining within $\pm 1\%$ across the investigated beam qualities. These results suggest that considerably wider acceptance limits may be required for TF than for the other XMM quantities when defining performance requirements in future standard updates.

Given the broad range of radiation conditions encountered in clinical practice, it is advisable to extend the test conditions used for limits of variation from the basic RQR radiation qualities to also include the newly proposed copper-filtered beam qualities representative of modern clinical imaging systems. Table 2 summarises the resulting performance criteria for field-class dosimeters proposed on the basis of the results reported in [8, 10, 11] and discussed above, covering all investigated quantities across the full range of clinically relevant radiation qualities. In addition, the table includes the corresponding manufacturer-stated accuracy (maximum permissible error) ranges for each quantity, enabling comparison between experimentally observed performance and current manufacturer specifications.

Table 2. Proposed limits of variation for energy dependence of response for field class dosimeters for all quantities and comparison with manufacturers stated accuracy.

	XMM quantity				
	Air kerma	Tube voltage	Half-value layer	Total filtration	Irradiation time
Limit of variation for photon energy (%)	5	5	10	15	1
Manufacturer stated accuracy range (%)	3.5 – 5	1.5 – 5	5 – 10	6 – 20	0.05 – 1
Manufacturer stated accuracy range (%) for mammography	2.5 – 5	1 – 2	5 – 10		

For air kerma, the same limits currently specified in IEC 61674 can also be applied to a wider range of radiation qualities, including the proposed copper-filtered beams. For tube voltage (TV), however, the acceptance limits should be extended if a broader range of radiation qualities is included in the test conditions. At present, IEC 61676 does not define performance requirements for several other XMM quantities, such as HVL, total filtration, and irradiation time. The inclusion of these quantities in future revisions of the standards

should therefore be considered, and the results presented here can serve as an initial basis for establishing corresponding performance criteria and limits of variation.

5.3 Summary of recommendations for mammography beams

In the field of mammography, several publications [12 –17] have provided data supporting the development of calibration protocols for mammography systems and have identified key uncertainty components arising from varying measurement conditions. When conditions are restricted to appropriate software selection and emphasis is placed on the energy dependence of detector response, the most relevant data are reported by Salomon et al. [15] and Costa de Castro et al. [13]. In addition to summarizing our research data, manufacturer-specified accuracy ranges are presented in Table 2.

Costa de Castro et al. [13] investigated six XMM models calibrated under both laboratory conditions (W/Al anode/filter) and clinical conditions (Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh), across four tube voltages (25 kV – 35 kV). Salomon et al. [15] examined five XMMs using nine different anode/filter combinations and the same tube voltage range (25 kV – 35 kV), effectively covering the full spectrum of radiation qualities used in current clinical practice. In this summary, energy dependence of XMM response is evaluated relative to 28 kV for each anode/filter combination. Additionally, responses across the entire range of radiation qualities are compared to the reference condition of Mo/Mo at 28 kV.

Both Costa de Castro et al. [13] and Salomon et al. [15] reported that variations specific to a given anode/filter combination were typically below 3 %. However, when considering the full range of anode/filter combinations, total variation increased to approximately 5 %. They also observed slightly larger variations under laboratory conditions and concluded that calibration coefficients derived under standardized laboratory settings cannot be directly transferred to clinical mammography. These findings support the adoption of a ± 5 % limit for energy dependence, consistent with dosimeters used in general radiology and as proposed in Table 2. Regarding tube voltage, Costa de Castro et al. [13] found that anode/filter-specific variations were generally below 3 %, although in a few cases they exceeded 5 %. Further investigation over a broader range of radiation qualities is still needed. However, the same ± 5 % limit applied in general radiology is currently considered appropriate.

For half-value layer (HVL), Costa de Castro et al. [13] reported anode/filter-specific variations typically below 3.5 %, though values exceeding 5 % were observed for some XMMs. Kojic et al [17] investigated the impact of field size on HVL for five XMMs with W/Rh and W/Ag anode/filter combinations. While the study primarily focused on field size effects, the energy dependence data can also be derived from the measured data. In most cases variations remained within 3 %, although one XMM exhibited larger variations of around 5 %. In the more extensive study, Salomon et al. [15] found that variations were below 6 % for individual anode/filter combinations but reached up to 8 % when evaluated over the full range of radiation qualities, with even higher deviations observed under certain laboratory conditions. Based on these findings, the same tolerance limits used in general radiology (Table 2) are considered appropriate for mammography when the

full clinical range is covered. When only a limited range of radiation qualities is considered, more stringent limits may be applied.

The observed variations depend on both the XMM model and the radiation quality and may also be influenced by the presence of a compression paddle. This demonstrates that nominally identical mammography beam qualities can differ significantly under practical clinical conditions. These findings highlight the need to account for clinically relevant spectral modifications when defining energy dependence tests and acceptance criteria for mammography XMMs in future revisions of IEC standards. Overall, the results confirm that energy dependence remains a significant source of uncertainty in mammography XMM measurements, with its magnitude depending on both the measured quantity and the specific device.

6 Adjusted beams

6.1 Changing tube voltage

In addition to the published studies, supplementary measurements were performed. The performance of the XMMs was evaluated in terms of small changes in tube voltage for all measured quantities under diagnostic (RQR 3, 5, 8 and 9) and mammography (WRh50 at 25 kV, 28 kV, 30 kV and 35 kV) radiation qualities in laboratory beams. The maximum percentage variation was calculated by comparing the calibration factor obtained when the tube voltage was changed by ± 1 kV from the qualities described above.

Small changes in tube voltage for RQR radiation qualities were evaluated for four XMM model types. The maximum percentage variation for all quantities for three of the XMMs tested was less than 0.5 %. However, for one XMM model (Nomex), the maximum variations for HVL and TF were substantially higher, at 1.4 % and 3.9 %, respectively.

Five different XMM models were tested for mammography radiation qualities. All XMMs presented a higher variation (up to 4.4 %) for quantities related to tube voltage at 24 kV, but the maximum variation for the other measured quantities was also less than 0.5 %.

6.2 Changing total filtration

The performance of the XMMs in terms of air kerma, average tube voltage and half-value layer was evaluated by increasing total filtration. In mammography, the influence of the added compression paddle was studied for six XMMs [13]. The compression paddle changed the response by a maximum of 8.7 % for air kerma, 4.8 % for HVL and 5.5 % for quantities related to tube voltage for Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh radiation qualities.

Another study quantified the sensitivity of the XMM calibration coefficients to changes in the X-ray spectra by adding PMMA of different thicknesses (2.0 mm – 4.8 mm) for Mo/Mo and W/Al radiation qualities. The evaluation was performed in relation to the calibration coefficients obtained without PMMA, and deviations of up to 10.0% were observed for the air kerma rate. However, substantially larger deviations were observed for tube voltage and half value layer, reaching up to 42.0 % and 43.0 %, respectively [16]. Although PMMA as a material and this thickness range may not fully represent typical compression paddles, the results clearly

demonstrated the presence of energy dependence in XMM response, even for nominally identical radiation qualities with the same anode/filter combination.

The performance of the XMMs in relation to changes in total filtration for diagnostic RQR radiation qualities was evaluated in clinical and laboratory beams by adding copper filtration to the RQR standard radiation qualities. Measurements in clinical beams were taken over an extensive range of copper filtration thicknesses (from 0.1 mm to 1.0 mm Cu in steps of 0.1 mm Cu) and radiation qualities (RQR 2 – 9). The maximum variation in air kerma, HVL and tube voltage due to changes in total filtration was found to be 6.0 % for air kerma and tube voltage, and 12.0 % for HVL. The same evaluation was performed in laboratory beams, but with a limited number of radiation qualities and copper filter thicknesses. The maximum variation was less than 6.0 %, 6.0%, 10.0 % and 10.0 % for K_{air} , TV, HVL and TF, respectively. As can be seen, the maximum variations obtained for each quantity are in the same range in both beams.

7 Proposal to update the IEC standards

Current IEC standards specify requirements for dosimeters measuring air kerma (IEC 61267) and PPV (IEC 61676), while requirements for other relevant quantities are not yet defined. We propose that the IEC requirements for the remaining quantities (half-value layer, average tube voltage, maximum peak voltage and irradiation time) should be included into IEC 61676. Furthermore, this standard should include clear and unambiguous definitions for these quantities. Additionally, consideration should be given to harmonizing the reference conditions for these measurements, aligning them with those defined in IEC 61674.

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